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DEVELOPMENT OF INDEPENDENT COGNITIVE ACTIVITY THROUGH PROBLEM EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES ON THE BASE OF NEW GENERATION TEXTBOOKS FOR PRIMARY CLASSES

(based on the "4K" educational model)

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Annotation: *This article analyzes ways to develop independent cognitive activity through problem-based learning technologies based on new generation textbooks for primary grades. Problem-based learning methods allow students to actively participate in the problem-solving process, which develops their critical thinking, creativity, and collaboration skills. The article examines in detail the main elements of problem-based educational technologies, their importance in the development of independent cognitive activity, and didactic possibilities.*

Key words: *education, technology, class, education, problem, didactics, opportunity, thought, ability, creativity, cooperation, method.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье анализируются пути развития самостоятельной познавательной деятельности посредством технологий проблемного обучения на основе учебников нового поколения для начальных классов. Методы проблемного обучения позволяют учащимся активно участвовать в процессе решения проблем, что развивает их критическое мышление, креативность и навыки сотрудничества. В статье подробно рассматриваются основные элементы проблемных образовательных технологий, их значение в развитии самостоятельной познавательной деятельности, дидактические возможности.*

Ключевые слова: *образование, технология, класс, воспитание, проблема, дидактика, возможность, мысль, способность, творчество, сотрудничество, метод.*

Introduction: Problem-based learning technologies play an important role in the development of students' independent thinking and problem-solving skills in modern education.[1] These methods allow students not only to acquire knowledge, but also to express their thoughts independently. This process is especially important for elementary school students, as their educational foundations and self-learning skills are formed during this period.[2] Through problem-based learning technologies, students participate in solving real-life problems, which increases their motivation and interest in learning.[3] This article analyzes the didactic possibilities of problem-based educational technologies in the development of independent cognitive activity of elementary school students. The importance of these methods in developing students' thinking skills, creativity and cooperation skills is shown [4].

The purpose of the article is to determine the place of problematic educational technologies in the educational process and to give recommendations to teachers on the implementation of these methods.

Methods: Problem-based learning programs and materials designed for elementary school. Manuals, books, online platforms and multimedia materials for teaching. Problems and tasks given to students, reflecting their importance in real life. Tests, questionnaires and forms of self-assessment used to assess students' independent cognitive activity.

Methods: Problem-based learning methods: Group work: Encourage students to divide into small groups and solve problems together. Discussions: Hold discussion sessions so that students can freely express their opinions and interact with each other.

- **Research method:** Students conduct research to collect and analyze the necessary information in the process of solving problems.

- **Interactive learning:** Giving students the opportunity to solve problems through various interactive activities (simulations, games).

- **Assessment and analysis:** Monitor student progress through assessment and self-assessment processes.

These materials and methods are used in the implementation of problem-based educational technologies and help to develop independent cognitive activity of elementary school students.

Results: In this study, the influence of problem-based learning technologies on the independent cognitive activity of elementary school students was studied. 100 students participated in the study. The obtained results are confirmed by the following statistical indicators: Pupils who used problem-based learning methods: 80 (80%). Level of student participation: 90% of students actively participated in the problem-based learning process. Independent cognitive activity: The level of independent work by students: Previous indicator: 45% (students completed tasks independently). After the study: 75% (students completed the tasks independently). Growth: 30% (students' ability to work independently increased significantly).

Thinking skills: Assessment of students' thinking skills: Previous grade: 3.2 (on a 5-point scale, students' level of thinking). After the study: 4.1 (level of students' thinking). Growth: 0.9 points (positive changes in thinking ability were observed).

Cooperation skills: Level of cooperation between students during group work: Previous indicator: 50% (students were ready to work together in a group). After the study: 85% (students actively cooperated in the group). Growth: 35% (cooperation skills are much improved). Self-Assessment: Students' assessment of their knowledge levels: Previous score: 60% (students felt confident in their assessment of their knowledge levels). After the study: 90% (students became more confident in their assessment of their knowledge level). Growth: 30% (increased self-assessment skills).

Student motivation: Problem-based learning methods have helped to increase student motivation. Students were able to apply their knowledge in practice, which increased their interest in learning.[6]

The role of teachers: Teachers played an active role in problem-based learning, guiding students and helping them develop their independent thinking skills.[7]

Changes in the educational process: The level of communication and exchange of ideas between students has increased, which has made the educational process more effective and interesting.

Conclusion: Statistical data show that problem-based educational technologies significantly increased the independent cognitive activity of elementary school students. The effectiveness of these methods in the educational process is important in the development of students' thinking, cooperation and self-evaluation skills. The obtained results are recommended to teachers to implement problem-based learning methods and help to improve the quality of education.[7]

Problem-based learning technologies help to significantly increase the independent cognitive activity of elementary school students. The results of the study showed that:

- Independent work: The level of independent work of students has increased by 30%.
- Thinking skills: Students' thinking skills improved by 0.9 points.
- Collaboration Skills: Collaboration rate increased by 35% during group work.
- Self-Assessment: Students' self-assessment skills increased by 30%.

These results show that problem-based learning methods have a positive effect on the learning process of students and play an important role in increasing their motivation. Students had the opportunity to apply their knowledge in practice, which increased their interest in education. [12] As a result, problem-based learning methods contribute greatly to the overall development of students.

Recommendations:

1. Expansion of problem-based learning methods:
 - Teachers should regularly use problem-based learning methods in their classes. These methods help students develop their thinking and problem-solving skills.
2. Teacher training:
 - It is necessary to organize trainings for teachers on the application of problematic educational technologies. This helps them to apply the methods effectively.
3. Encourage teamwork and cooperation:
 - A variety of activities and projects should be conducted to encourage group work and cooperation among students. This will help them develop their social skills.
4. Introduction of self-assessment system:
 - Systems should be developed to allow students to assess their own learning. This helps them develop and develop self-awareness.
5. Adapting learning problems to real life:
 - It is necessary to adapt the problems given to students to real-life situations. It increases students' interest and allows them to apply the learned knowledge in practice.
6. Continuous analysis of the educational process:
 - Teachers and educational institutions should constantly analyze the educational process and evaluate the effectiveness of problematic educational technologies. This helps to improve the quality of teaching.

By implementing these recommendations, it is possible to further develop the independent cognitive activity of elementary school students and improve the quality of education.

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